

Study Relationship between TQM on Empowerment and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract—Today, quality improvement is an essential manner that is notified primarily as an essence in industry, manufacturing, health and education. Whenever quality is noticed as a criterion, then it results into empowering managers and job satisfaction of staffs. The research is aimed to evaluate the rate of relationship between TQM executions toward rate of empowering and satisfaction of staff paper mill in Isfahan. Results showed that there is a meaningful relationship between TQM, empowerment and satisfaction and even between TQM and empowerment dimensions; total quality management can perfectly predict empowerment and job satisfaction.

Keywords—TQM (total quality management), Empowerment, Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

TQM is one of the common expressions in management and it is a system that all its components are completely harmonized, proportional, having scientific value and to do activity is based on collaboration and cooperation of staffs and even managers of that company. By using group capabilities and talents of managers and even staffs, it is resulted into persistent quality improvement and organization efficiency [5]. Today, quality improvement is an essential manner that is notified primarily as an essence in industry [20] manufacturing [15], [16] health [22], and education [21]. Main emphasis of this method is that all staffs and managers attempt on regular improvement of service quality and accordant goods with customers' demands [3]. On the other word, total integration is being noticed and it will follow up common responsibility between managers and staffs to respond to appropriate quality [13].

II. RESEARCH LITERATURE

A. Total Quality Management

Quality concept is rooted into industrial experts' activities. Quality importance was notified in 1940 and 1950. It was firstly applied in production and then in service sections [4]. Feigenbaum, innovator of total quality control, defines quality as ability of a product to gain considered targets manufactured with least possible costs. Edward Deming, Philip Crosby, Josef Juran and Taguchi Vasshi are as the most famous leaders in quality hypothesis who have had significant impacts on today world industry [19]. Deming has expressed customer satisfaction and change decreasing in quality

definition [1] and Crosby defines quality as concordance of a product or service with predetermined requirements (features and standards) [9].

TQM is a comprehensive concept that causes persistent improvement in company [14]. TQM philosophy emphasizes organizational systematic, consistent, stable and total perspectives and its scope is so broaden. The system is basically emphasis on internal and external total customer satisfaction, however, it attempts on continuous improvement of systems and processes in management classes [10]. TQM application brings about various values. Relationship between empowerment and customer satisfaction of staffs with TQM is studied in the research.

B. Staffs Empowerment

Empowerment means conferment of authority in organizational roles that the authority must be dedicated to individual or organizational roles. Empowerment means individual enthuse to admit responsibility of an entry that firstly was officially interpreted into respond meaning [2]. When quality principles were mentioned by Japanese in 60s, western countries were keen on it in 80s. The principles expressed empowering and training personals and staffs [7]. By TQM, nurse roles regarding to quality control were allocated to staff, and empowering and training of them will be accepted. Therefore, staffs learn quality management techniques and broadly it is focused on staffs and matrons training [11].

C. Customer Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a set of emotion and believes that people have about their current occupation. It is one of the main aspects in job success, the aspect that results into more efficiencies and also individual satisfaction [12].

Reference [6] considered job satisfaction as innate manner and mentioned it as a kind of emotional adjustment with occupation and job status. It m meant if considered occupation provides appropriate enjoyment, the one will be satisfied of that. In contrast, if considered occupation are not be able to satisfy the ones, so s/he may complain about one's job and attempts to change it. Researchers are trying to find fundamental reasons for job satisfaction in companies for a long time. However, they can recently obtain stable and related manners in job satisfaction, but obtaining to total empirical pattern haven't been achieved [8].

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III. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Instability in management, company managers alters and lack of codified processes and observation systems on process operation will cause that organization can't report continuous improvement trends of process and their operation. Objective criteria and information result into managers are not able to use ambiguous information in their strategic decision-making and planning. TQM had significant impacts on industrial companies. Contrarily, lack of attention to TQM criteria resulted into diminishing level of quality in mills and even occurring organizational disorders. The research is therefore aimed to study relationship between TQM with empowerment and job satisfaction so that TQM potentials and their impacts on improving these two aspects are being distinguished.

A. Problem Importance

Organization environment changes and change in organization and its requirements cause to pay more attention into various perspectives of quality. However, importance of quality in productive organizations and mills, because of gaining global standards, causes that quality plays significant roles in organizations. Integrated use of values resulted into raising quality and getting awarded of potentials caused that importance of it is being more obvious.

B. Research Aims

- Study relationship between TQM and staff empowerment
- Study relationship between TQM and staff job satisfaction

C. Research Hypotheses

- There is a meaningful relationship between TQM and staff empowerment.
- There is a meaningful relationship between TQM and staff job satisfaction.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is descriptive survey. Statistical society of the research is all official staffs of paper mills in Isfahan in 1390. All are 300 persons that to determine capacity of the sample regarding to the fact that there were no ration between agrees and disagrees, first of all by 30 basic questionnaires above mentioned ration was obtained and then by this Cook ran formulation, sample capacity of 119 persons were given.

$$n = \frac{(300)(1.96)(1.96)(0.5)(0.5)}{(299)(0.07)(0.07) + (1.96)(1.96)(0.5)(0.5)} = 119$$

To study research questions in the research, three questionnaires of TQM, empowerment and satisfaction are used. In TQM questionnaire, three kinds of distance, range and nominal scale are used and include five perspectives as commitment, customer, train, cooperation and evaluation. This scale is used for empowerment questionnaire of staffs. This scale includes six criteria as decision-making, efficacy, effectiveness, autonomy, databases and professional growth. For job satisfaction, Minnesota questionnaire of job

satisfaction is used that this questionnaire was made by [23] and has two internal and external infrastructures.

Between 119 distributed questionnaires, 112 ones were given back that 100 out of them had been usable.

V. RESEARCH FINDINGS

To study relationship between TQM with empowerment and job satisfaction of staffs, correlation coefficient of Pierson and regression analysis is simultaneously used.

A. Hypothesis I: There Is a Meaningful Relationship between TQM and Empowerment of Staffs

Regarding given results in Table I, correlation coefficient between TQM and empowerment is given 0.401. Accordingly meaningfulness of correlation coefficient in 0.001 level, it can be concluded that quality management has positive and meaningful relationship with empowerment. Thus, researched evidences approve hypothesis 1.

B. Hypothesis II: There Is a Meaningful Relationship between TQM and Job Satisfaction of Staffs

Regarding given results in Table II, correlation coefficient between TQM and job satisfaction is given 0.339. Given correlation coefficient in Table II is at the meaningful level of ($p \leq 0.004$). Thus, it can be concluded that there is positive and meaningful relationship between quality management and empowerment of staffs. Researched evidence approve hypothesis 2.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Hypothesis I

To study amount of relationship between TQM and empowerment of staffs, Pierson correlation coefficient is used. Given results in Table I states relationship between TQM with empowerment of staffs by correlation coefficient of 0.401 and meaningful level of 0.001 that this proved hypothesis 1 completely approves relationship between TQM and empowerment of staffs.

Result of the research with subject of TQM as competitive benefit shows that most characters that are in relation with TQM such as quality training, processes development and benchmarking never provide total benefits but problems made in TQM such as open culture, empowerment of staffs and execution commitments results into some benefits [17]. Empowerment of staffs, in the research, is resulted from TQM making. Therefore, research conclusion is as the same as research on paper making mills in Isfahan.

B. Hypothesis II

Pierson correlation coefficient is used to study hypothesis 2. Given results in Table II states relationship between TQM with job satisfaction of staffs by correlation coefficient of 0.33 and meaningful level of 0.001. Thus hypothesis 2 is approved and it is proven that quality management is able to enhance people satisfaction and in sum by expanding satisfaction, job quality will improve, too. Research aimed to study related manners into people in TQM and job satisfaction concluded

that there is a significant relationship between people oriented elements in TQM with job satisfaction. In the research, importance of related people aspects in TQM is also to be stated for predicting job satisfaction [18]. Equivalence in above results is distinguished based research on paper making mall in Isfahan.

In thesis about TQM techniques impact on job satisfaction of staffs in Malaysia it is concluded that staffs must be encouraged to cooperate in paving and doing TQM in organizations. This matter can be due to job satisfaction in staffs of organization [24]. These results alignments with research results in paper making mall in Isfahan is obviously given.

TABLE I

AMOUNT OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TQM AND EMPOWERMENT OF STAFFS

Variables	Average	Standard deviation	Numbers	Correlation coefficient	Meaningful level
Quality management	1.02	10.42	77		
Empowerment	1.48	19.17	78	0.041	0.001

TABLE II

AMOUNT OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TQM AND JOB SATISFACTION OF STAFFS

Variables	Average	Standard deviation	Numbers	Correlation coefficient	Meaningful level
Quality management	1.02	10.42	77		
Job satisfaction	-14.46	12.78	83	0.339	0.004

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